

Superior hue output as well as lumen for WLEDs with dual-sheet distant layouts of phosphor

Phuc Dang Huu¹, Phan Xuan Le²

¹Institute of Applied Technology, Thu Dau Mot University, Binh Duong Province, Vietnam

²Faculty of Mechanical - Electrical and Computer Engineering, School of Engineering and Technology, Van Lang University, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

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ABSTRACT

Remote phosphor constructions usually have color quality drawbacks but are more luminous in terms of lumen, surpassing conformal phosphor or in-cup layouts of phosphor. From this disadvantage, there is a great number of studies carried out to boost the chromatic performance in remote phosphor (RP) structures. This work focuses on using a two-layer RP or dual-film RP (DFRP) to improve the color rendering indices (CRI) as well as color quality scales (CQS) for white light emitting diodes (WLEDs). Two equivalent dual remote phosphor (DRP) structures for WLEDs operating at various temperatures of color including 5600 K, 7000 K, as well as 8500 K will be employed for our study. The study's idea involves putting one phosphor $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ layer or one red phosphor $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ layer on top of the yellow $\text{YAG}:\text{Ce}^{3+}$. Subsequently modifying the concentration for each red and green phosphor to investigate the changes in color metrics and luminous flux. As a result, a suitable red and green phosphor concentration can be determined to acquire desired outcomes for each DFRP-WLED. Obtained results show that $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ performs significant boosting on both CRI and CQS, especially when being integrated with increasing concentration, thanks to the increased red-light presence for the WLED device. In addition, the sheet of phosphor $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ benefits the luminous flux.

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Corresponding Author:

Phan Xuan Le

Faculty of Mechanical - Electrical and Computer Engineering, School of Engineering and Technology

Van Lang University, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

Email: le.px@vlu.edu.vn

1. INTRODUCTION

Semiconductor diodes, which utilize the light-conversion from the integrated phosphors to generate phosphor-converted white light-emitting diodes (pc-WLEDs), are considered a promising fourth-generation illuminating supply to be able to substitute the traditional one. This type of semiconductor diodes can be diversely employed in illumination [1]-[3]. Whereas the luminous intensity (LI) and correlated chromatic temperatures' uniformity (CCTU) in pc-WLEDs still demonstrate considerable limitation, though they have become increasingly common in various diverse domains of our everyday lives, such as billboard, traffic lighting, and backlighting [4]-[6]. Further improvements in illuminating effectiveness and color standard are required according to the market's and applications' increasing needs [7]. The most typical method for producing illumination in white nowadays involves combining yellow illumination emitted by the yellow-emitting phosphor and the blue illumination generated by a light emitting diode (LED) chip. Despite the fact that this design seems to have good lighting brightness, the layout for the LED, as well as the placement for sheets of phosphor have a considerable effect in defining illuminating effectiveness, particularly the color rendering

index (CRI) [8]-[10]. For the production of WLEDs, many popular processes for forming phosphorus surface coatings were suggested, including dispensing and conformal coatings [11], [12]. However, owing to the loss in luminous converting of phosphor material produced by a rise in heat generation at the LED and phosphor layer interface when the yellow phosphor layer was directly placed above the LED chip, resulting in greater temperature for the LED device as well as the phosphor sheet interface, these architectures do not give excellent color standard. As a result, lowering the heat output would increase phosphor efficiency while avoiding permanent phosphor degradation. Much prior research has shown that using a distant phosphor configuration, where the phosphor becomes distant from the thermal source (LED chip), the thermal influence can be reduced. LEDs may prevent backscatter and light circulation if the space separating the phosphor and the LED chip was big enough. Such a method is an ideal way of managing LED heat, as a result, to improve the illuminating efficacy and color intensity of LEDs [13]-[15]. Nevertheless, while the distant phosphor configuration is adequate for general illumination, it may not fulfill the needs of various other illuminating uses, which is likely why a new improvement for LEDs is required. Some new distant phosphor constructions are suggested for future improvement so that it is possible to lower phosphor reverse scattering aiming at the chip as well as to increase illuminating efficacy. Additional analysis revealed that an inverted cone lens encasement as well as a ring distant phosphor sheet around the LED chip may lead lighting generated by the chip of the LED to the LED exterior, lowering the degradation resulting from inner backscattering within the LED device [16], [17]. Greater angular-dependent CCTU and chromatic consistency are achievable with a patterned remote phosphor (RP) having a clear region without a daubing phosphorus film for the bordering area [18]. Furthermore, in comparison to a typical pattern, the patterned sapphire substrate utilized in the RP could give significantly greater far-field CCTU [19]. To increase the luminous intensity of LEDs, a distant phosphor with dual-film remote phosphor (DFRP) packaging is presented. The previous research aimed at enhancing the chromatic homogeneity and illuminating beam of WLEDs with a distant phosphor configuration. These experiments, however, are limited to single-chip WLED models with low color temperatures. Meanwhile, it's difficult to improve the optic parameter for WLEDs at significant color temperature. Moreover, there has been no study performed to compare the efficacy of various dual-layer phosphor designs. As a result, selecting a strategy to increase color standard or illuminating beam is extremely challenging for producers.

This paper discusses using two DFRP configurations for heightening the chromatic performance in WLEDs operating at various hue temperatures measured at 5600 K, 7000 K, as well as 8500 K. The first idea is to boost the green spectral energy inside a WLED by integrating green-phosphor $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ film, which will lead to greater luminescent intensity (LI). The second idea is to get the red-spectra enhancement by using a red phosphor film of $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ in WLED packaging, which will lead to greater color rendering metrics including color rendering indices and color quality scales, abbreviated as CRI and color quality scales (CQS), respectively. Our research will thoroughly demonstrate the chemical composition of $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ influencing the light attributes in WLEDs as well. The results show the improvements in both CRI and CQS with the presence of the $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ sheet. However, when concentrations of $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ and $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ are excessive, the degradation in lighting efficiency will be initiated. Thus, it is necessary to manipulate and keep their concentrations under suitable numbers, which eliminates such unwanted drawbacks. During this work, three differences when introducing a red or green sheet of phosphor above one YAG: Ce^{3+} film are observed: one is an increased red or blue illumination composition that increases the emission spectrum for the white-illumination band, a key to increasing chromatic performance. Second, the optical dispersion and propagation inside WLEDs can be inversely proportional to the added phosphors' concentration. Therefore, suitable phosphor concentrations become important for keeping the WLEDs' lumen.

2. PREPARATION

2.1. Preparation of $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ and $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ particles

The optic characteristics of phosphors are strongly influenced by their chemical composition. As a result, while applying to WLEDs, each of their components must be thoroughly examined. At peak wavelengths of 2.04 and 2.35 eV, $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ emits a green-orange light. The presence of the Mn^{2+} ion contributes to the higher luminous efficiency of $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$. Furthermore, $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ emits red light and its peak wavelength is 1.88 eV. The presence of an emission peak indicates that the red phosphor material $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ is more efficient, implying that the optic efficiency is greater [20], [21]. A spectral match with the blue light from the chip of LED must be required for these phosphors to be effective. These phosphors' absorption spectrum must match the blue chip's emission spectrum. $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ has a very excellent absorption spectrum for absorbing light emitted in many bands. Because the yellow phosphor layer

converts both blue and yellow light, not only blue light is generated. Likewise, the absorption spectrum of $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ ranges from 2.04 to 2.35 eV, with an absorption efficiency of greater than 70%.

Prior to doing an optic simulation of the particles $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ and $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$, the input factors, consisting of the concentration, granule measurement, excitation spectrum, absorption spectrum, as well as discharge spectrum of phosphor, must be experimentally investigated. Phosphor concentration and size are the unknown that must be discovered in order to get the best-LED color and illuminating beam quality [22]-[23]. The spectral properties do not change over time. The sizes of the phosphor particles are fixed on average at 14.5 μm , based on the outcomes of the earlier investigation. Meanwhile, the concentrations of the phosphors $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ and $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ need to be calibrated for determining the optimal value. Hence, this work is carried out to fulfill this objective.

2.2. Designing packages of green-yellow DFRP and red-yellow DFRP

Two DFRP-WLED models integrating nine LED chips are utilized for this work, as indicated in Figure 1. Each of these blue chips has a power reaching 1.16 W as well as a peak wavelength reaching 453 nm. Figure 1(a) and Figure 1(b) show the physical LED configuration and its optic parameters in detail, respectively. The next stage is to create distant phosphor models to determine the appropriate amounts of $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ and $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$. Two green-yellow DFRP and red-yellow DFRP models, shortened as GYRP and RYRP, respectively, are offered in this research. A pair of phosphor sheets are positioned above the blue chips to make up the GYRP structure. We place the $\text{YAG}:\text{Ce}^{3+}$ sheet above the $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ sheet, which can be seen via Figure 1(c). Similarly, the phosphor films of $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ and $\text{YAG}:\text{Ce}^{3+}$ comprising the RYRP configuration, demonstrated via Figure 1(d), are positioned on the LED chip cluster, in which the red $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ is above yellow $\text{YAG}:\text{Ce}^{3+}$. Both GYRP and RYRP profiles are employed to boost the color standard and illuminating beam of WLEDs. The increase of the red and green light dispersion and combination in WLEDs is critical to obtain this. Moreover, $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ and $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ concentrations must be changed substantially. Figure 2 shows the concentrations of blue phosphorus $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$, red phosphorus $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$, and yellow phosphorus $\text{YAG}:\text{Ce}^{3+}$ changing in the opposite direction. The first is that mean correlated color temperature (CCTs) will be maintained as a result of this adjustment. Secondly, the dispersion, along with the absorptivity for the pair of phosphor sheets in WLEDs would be altered by this change. This can considerably influence the WLEDs' color intensity and illuminating beam. The color intensity of WLEDs is thus determined by the concentrations of $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ and $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ used. $\text{YAG}:\text{Ce}^{3+}$ concentrations were lowered to maintain CCTs average when $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ and $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ concentrations rose from 2 wt% – 20 wt%. (Figure 2(a)) and 2 wt% – 26 wt%. (Figure 2(b)). The WLED devices under varying hue temperatures measured at 6600 K as well as 7700 K show the same phenomenon.

Lead frame: 4.7 mm Jentech Size-S

LED chip: V45H

Die attach: Sumitomo 1295SA

Gold Wire: 1.0 mil

Phosphor: ITC NYAG4_EL

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 1. Illustrations of pc-WLEDs: (a) the actual MCW-LED, (b) its parameters, (c) DFRP using $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$, and (d) DFRP using $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$

Figure 2. Concentrations of yellow-emitting phosphor YAG:Ce³⁺ in (a) green-yellow DFRP (GYRP) and (b) red-yellow DFRP (RYRP) for keeping the average CCTs

The influence of Mg₂SiO₄:Mn²⁺ concentrations on emission spectra of WLEDs is clearly depicted in Figure 3. A decision is made based on the specifications of the producers. WLEDs with high color intensity standards can lower illuminance by a tiny amount. The quantity of Zn₂SiO₄:Mn²⁺,P increased the intensity trend in the two light spectral ranges 420 nm – 480 nm as well as 500 nm – 640 nm. Such a rise of the discharge spectra of these two areas indicates a rise in the illuminance emitted. In addition, the scattering of emitted blue lights in WLEDs increases, i.e. scattering in both layers of phosphor and in WLEDs increases, resulting in favor of color uniformity. When using Zn₂SiO₄:Mn²⁺,P, this is an essential result. The trend in the spectral red element in the range between 648 and 738 nm surges alongside the Mg₂SiO₄:Mn²⁺ content, as can be seen. However, without a rise in the emission spectra for the remaining zones, 420 nm – 480 nm along with 500 nm – 640 nm, this is not significant. The 420 nm – 480 nm dual-band emission spectral rise aids in increasing blue-light scattering. A wider emission spectrum is represented by a greater color temperature. As a result, color standard and illuminating beam are improved. When using Mg₂SiO₄:Mn²⁺, this is the most essential outcome. Notably, manipulating the WLEDs' chromatic performance at great temperatures can be particularly burdensome [24]. This study confirms that Mg₂SiO₄:Mn²⁺ can enhance the color standard of WLEDs even at 5600 K and 8500 K hue temperatures.

Figure 3. Emission spectra of WLEDs

3. COMPUTATION AND DISCUSSION

When light reaches an object, the CRI determines its true color. The color unbalance between red, blue, green, and yellow colors, the primary color shades essential to the white-light formation, is caused by an excessive rise of green light. This has an impact on the white-light chromaticity of pc-LEDs, resulting in lower color fidelity. The CRI decreases slightly as the Zn₂SiO₄:Mn²⁺,P concentration starts to increase, which can be seen in Figure 4(a). However, because CRI is merely a decent element of CQS, this is acceptable. It is harder to acquire the CQS index, which would be more essential than CRI. As the Zn₂SiO₄:Mn²⁺,P concentration is less than 8%, CQS does not change (Figure 4). Thus, Zn₂SiO₄:Mn²⁺,P when being integrated into the DFRP package should keep a concentration less than or equal to 8 wt%, so that the CQS consistency is possibly accomplished.

In all three typical CCTs of Figure 4(b), the CRI value rose with the phosphor concentration $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$, displayed via the absorptivity for the layer of red phosphor. These red phosphor particles absorb LED-emitted blue lights and convert them to red light. $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ particles also absorb yellow light, but according to the material's absorption features, this red-emitting phosphor performs greater blue light absorption than the yellow absorption. And so, the WLEDs' red element is boosted with the addition of $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$, leading to greater CRI. In modern WLED selection parameters, CRI can be considered among the critical optical assessments. This probably results in the fact that superior CRI will make a WLED device more costly in the lighting market. Fortunately, using phosphor material such as $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ to stimulate the CRI factor of the WLED has the benefit of cost-effectiveness, making it applicable in mass production.

As demonstrated, the high CRI cannot assure the high color quality for the white light, since it is just a component for assessing another color metric of WLEDs – CQS. Particularly, CRI is a part of CQS which also combines the aspects of viewer preference and the coordination of the chromatic gamut [25]-[27]. This indicates the wider coverage of CQS, making it almost a real universal color quality measure. The augmentation of CQS in the presence of the distant phosphor layer $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ is shown in Figure 5(a). CQS increased considerably when $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ concentrations were raised. Obviously, the use of $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ could initiate the growth of color intensity of WLEDs with a DFRP configuration. This result can be the importance of using the red phosphor layer of $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ to boost the DFRP-WLED's color intensity. Nonetheless, the drawback in LI that may happen when using high-concentration $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ should be looked out. In contrast, the increase in green-phosphor $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ in the GYRP structure does not benefit the CQS of the WLED as it causes a drop in this parameter, as presented in Figure 5(b).

Generally, the WLED with great color performance could lower its luminous intensity by a small value and vice versa. Therefore, it is vital to demonstrate the luminous tendency of the two DFRPs to understand and figure out the best concentration for each phosphor in use. According to Figure 3, the GYRP is likely to be capable of enhancing the luminous flux since the blue emission intensity is higher than that of the RYRP one. The luminous fluxes of two DFRPs are demonstrated in Figure 6.

We can observe from Figure 6 that WLEDs with dual-layer distant phosphor have a higher luminous efficiency than those with single-layer phosphor. As a result, the effectiveness of the emitted light beam of these DFRPs has been shown in this article. Figure 6(a) indicates that with the increase of the $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ concentration (2 wt% – 20 wt%), the generated lighting beam increased dramatically. The concentration for the $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ sheet will also substantially impact the lighting beam of the DFRP. Apparently, through employing the law of Lambert-Beer, the attenuation coefficient μ_{ext} increases accordingly to the $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ content, while displaying an opposite behavior for the illumination propagation power. As such, by adjusting the breadth of these phosphor films in WLEDs, the luminous flux declines as the $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ content rises. We can clearly see in Figure 6(b) that the lumen is lowered at all three CCTs. As the $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ concentration is at 26 wt%, the reduction of LI is outstanding. Considering the benefits of the layer of red $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$, such as greater CRI as well as CQS, in line with the superior lumen power to that of the SFRP (without red phosphor layer), the decreasing LI in the RYRP configuration can be accepted. The remaining issue is dependent on the manufacturer's objective of selecting the optimal $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ concentration for mass manufacturing of these WLEDs.

Figure 4. Color rendering indices of (a) GYRP and (b) RYRP as a function of modifying $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ and $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ concentrations, respectively

Figure 5. The color quality scale of (a) GYRP and (b) RYRP as a function of modifying $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ and $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ concentrations, respectively

Figure 6. The luminous flux of (a) GYRP and (b) RYRP as a function of modifying $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ and $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ concentrations, respectively

4. CONCLUSION

The effects of the green phosphor $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ and the red phosphor $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ on the CRI, CQS, and LI of two DFRP structures are discussed for the research. The research has shown that $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ is a great option for improving color intensity, through employing the scattering theory of Mie theory as well as the law of Lambert-Beer. Besides, WLEDs use $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ as a luminous flux enhancement material. This applies not just to WLEDs at 5600 K, but also to WLEDs at 8500 K or higher. As a result, the findings yielded by our research could attain the objective of enhancing white light color intensity, which is hard to do using the distant-phosphor structure. The emitted luminous flux does, however, have a little disadvantage. The color intensity and luminous flux are greatly diminished as the $\text{Zn}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+},\text{P}$ or $\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{2+}$ concentration is significantly raised. As a result, depending on the manufacturer's objectives, selecting an appropriate concentration becomes critical. Our research has provided useful data to create WLEDs with higher performance.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Phuc Dang Huu received a Physics Ph.D. degree from the University of Science, Ho Chi Minh City, in 2018. Currently, he is Research Institute of Applied Technology, Thu Dau Mot University, Binh Duong Province, Vietnam. His research interests include simulation LEDs material, renewable energy. He can be contacted at email: danghuuphuc@tdmu.edu.vn.

Phan Xuan Le received a Ph.D. in Mechanical and Electrical Engineering from Kunming University of Science and Technology, Kunming city, Yunnan province, China. Currently, He is a lecturer at the Faculty of Engineering, Van Lang University, Ho Chi Minh City, Viet Nam. His research interests are Optoelectronics (LED), Power transmission and Automation equipment. He can be contacted at email: le.px@vlu.edu.vn and phanxuanle.ts@gmail.com.